

УДК 365.4,728.1,728.34

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DEVELOPMENT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE LANDED-HOUSING IN BINTAN ISLAND, INDONESIA

Abstract. Indonesia is a rapidly developing country, the fourth largest in the world in terms of population and the fourteenth in terms of area, while having an uneven population density in different regions. The urgency of building energy-efficient housing in western Indonesia is caused, on the one hand, by the need to create new settlements for the resettlement of residents from the most overcrowded areas and, on the other hand, by providing them with environmentally friendly renewable energy sources. The paper analyzes the island of Bintan – the largest island in the province of Kepulauan Riau, located on the border with Singapore and Malaysia, characterized by exotic nature and climate and has great tourism, cultural and industrial potential. The aim of the study is to develop recommendations for the design of low-rise housing on Bintan Island, taking into account the efficient use of resources, the protection of biodiversity and the ecological integrity of natural resources in the region. The recommendations have a three-level hierarchy, including aspects of territorial development, features of the volumetric and spatial structure of buildings and structures, as well as characteristics of the materials used.

Keywords: regional climate, settlement and building development, sustainable landed-housing, green design recommendation.

1. Relevance. Climate change is an undeniable matter that has an impact on global warming, one of which is the main contributor to the building and construction sector in which reports for 36% of total global energy consumption then in detailed about 22% is consumed in the housing sector. Besides that, emissions from the housing sector is 17 % in 2020 [1]. Although, the use of fossil energy for electricity production is non-renewable energy and its dominant use causes many negative consequences that can result in environmental damage and excessive carbon dioxide emissions resulting in a shortage of clean water, soil and air, thereby changing the global climate.

Afterwards, as with other developing countries, Indonesia's energy supply system continues to be dominated by non-renewable energy, so a breakthrough is needed to reduce dependence on it. Then knowledge about effective measures to reduce energy consumption in settlements, especially in housing through climate-responsive design and efficient technology, it is still low in planning and implementation in most parts of Indonesia.

2. Definition of landed-housing. In real estate, a landed property or landed estate is a property that generates income for the owner (typically a member of the gentry) without the owner having to do the actual work of the estate [6]. Meanwhile, a housing estate (or sometimes housing complex or housing development) is a group of homes and other buildings built together as a single development then the exact form may vary from country to country [5]. Based on that, it can be interpreted that a landed house is a dwelling built directly on the ground, then each landed house unit stands independently without counting the levels. In contrast, an apartment which are located in high-rise buildings, they are often also called vertical dwellings.

In Indonesia, the existence of landed-housing is more intended for lower-middle social communities so that the Indonesian government holds a program of "building a million houses". Based

on the National Medium-Term Development (RPJMN) 2020–2024 with target of 70 percent of households living in decent houses or as many as 11 million households [3].

On the other hand, often landed-housing development is only oriented to the function of a physical place to live, but it does not pay attention to environmental physical infrastructure facilities and resource facilities such as; electricity, water and sanitation so that housing is not abandoned by its inhabitants because it is unfit for habitation and uncomfortable to live in. Finally, this it will have an impact on the emergence of slum areas in the territory. In short, to achieve the objectives then the following stages of research were carried out:

The hypothetical framework of the landed-housing;

Discussion of recommendation;

Conclusions and suggestion

3. The hypothetical framework of sustainable the landed-housing. In developing an integrated residential site in Bintan island, it will be related to the residential environment and the building itself, so it takes a framework of identified elements that it can represent the specification object as an initial hypothesis. Therefore, this research will be divided into 2 (two) main subjects, namely.

3.1. Methods. A low-energy house is characterized by an energy-efficient design and technical features which enable it to provide high living standards and comfort with low energy consumption and carbon emissions [7], various approaches have emerged for methods of increasing energy efficiency in housing, both in energy-responsive and environmentally friendly buildings then the design focuses more on energy-efficient design as one of the values in the "green design" concept which is concentrated on the architecture of the building and its environment by paying attention to the efficient use of resources, starting from architectural design for sites and buildings that its are adapted to the surrounding climate by selecting sustainable materials and use of intelligent technology that helps save resources [2].

Therefore, the methods of bioclimatic architecture and green architecture is needed to be able to bring up energy-efficient design. That it is mean green architecture usually focuses on the use of recyclable materials, renewable energy, and minimizes waste and energy consumption, which means that the use of energy systems that are capable of generating their own electricity in buildings is very much needed while bioclimatic architecture is related to aspects biological and climatic conditions such as thermal comfort and some passive design strategies thus methods that allow buildings to use their surrounding environment for heating and ventilation.

3.2. Characteristics. Bintan island is located between 01° 00' north latitude 1°20' south latitude and 104°00' east longitude 108°30' west longitude with tropical climate and lowest average temperature of 23.9 °C with an air humidity of around 85%. In specific, the physical characteristic of the Bintan island is tropical rainforest climate or equatorial climate basically, so they experience high mean annual temperatures, small temperature ranges, and rain that falls throughout the year [8]. A tropical rainforest climate is typically hot, very humid, and wet like wise of it is no distinct wet or dry seasons as rainfall is high throughout the months then sometimes one day in can be very similar to the next days, while the change in temperature between day and night may be larger than the average change in temperature during the year. Moreover, most of the land is not very fertile, and also the soil is red because it is rich in iron so that it will have an impact on the heat island effect which can cause significant temperature changes.

The social characteristic of the settlements in the almost territory in Bintan islands as characterized by the collective activity of fishermen as main live hood, then sometimes their change live hood as craftsmen and gardeners. In the context of community with different similar origins, especially family and cultural relations, there are various similarities in the implementation of community and building forms, both in physically and spatially. Furthermore, it is categorized as suburban in terms of visualization of the territory. This is reflected in the physical condition of community and residential buildings so associated with the quality of the area is related, social and cultural values, so that the location of residential areas is formed with the concept of neighborhood.

Fig. 1. Framework of sustainable the landed-housing

Based on the description of the subject of the functional model scheme that the following factors are obtained: territory, building and materials [4] so that the principles of combining the bioclimatic architecture and green architecture methods can be applied. Furthermore, both in physical characteristics as microclimate and social characteristics as culture and people behavior provide an overview of the environmental conditions of the community as the basis for developing the green design concept.

4. Discussion of recommendation. Basically sustainable landing-housing is the goal of the basic concept of green design carried out with an ecological approach so that the territory and building can utilize water and energy resources both in effectively and efficiently, reduce waste, implement an integrated transportation system, ensure environmental health, and synergize the natural environment and artificial in a design that it is oriented to the principles of sustainable development: environmental, social, and economic.

Therefore, to achieve the objectives described above, there are 3 component aspects that have been determined:

4.1. Territory. Divided of micro-neighbourhoods into five levels: settlement, institutional neighborhood, residential neighborhood, housing cluster and house [9] are the basis for the concept of landed-housing sustainability by taking into account several aspects, namely: site processing, provision of pedestrian routes, transportation methods area, movement circulation, conservation and distribution system of energy, water and waste. So it is demanded how to modify an area, both in the form of landscape and vegetation in order to be able to reduce radiation from the impact of greenhouse gas emissions by grouping land and buildings so that it can emphasize the shape and orientation of the building mass. Furthermore, pedestrian paths and bicycle paths must be provided adequately in terms of dimensions and comfort of use with the use of protective trees so that road users will not be directly exposed to sunlight. In line with that, the establishment of playgrounds and recreation parks as green areas starting at the residential neighborhood level to housing clusters.

4.2. Building. The orientation of the building is oriented from east to west along the path of the sun, only showing a small facade towards the sun. which openings (doors, windows, ventilation) should face north or south to reduce solar radiation, but if the openings face east and west then protected with shade or trees to reduce radiation in the form of greater distances between houses so that air circulation occurs the good one. Furthermore, to reduce heat from the east and west, the thick walls are made of massive construction materials or composite materials with high thermal insulation. The models and types of roofs use composite materials with high thermal insulation in order to reflect solar radiation, as well as a protruding roof to shade the facades and windows. On the other hand, the use of energy sources by installing a solar power system on the roof for electricity needs and for rainwater treatment so that it can be used as sink water.

4.3. Material. Environmentally friendly building materials are currently needed for the purpose of reducing energy consumption, emissions and waste so that renewable materials are needed, such as: modified bamboo to absorb heat on walls, window frames and door frames using aluminum material which has the advantage of being recyclable, and free of toxins so that it is easy to maintain, the use of mild steel in the framework of the main building and roof which has the advantage of being stronger and lighter so that it does not burden the construction and foundation. Furthermore, the principle of ecological use in outdoor areas, in this case minimizing the use of road pavement in the form of asphalt or concrete with the use of grassblock material in order to absorb heat on the ground surface and the use of vegetation according to its function, such as: guiding plants that have a single log and tree shape tall, non-woody plants with stems and leaves that are able to store air reserves and are resistant to dry conditions, and shade plants in the form of trees with branches that are more than 2 meters high to provide shade to the house and prevent glare from the sun. Last but not least, the use of energy-efficient equipment, namely LEDs (light-emitting diodes) which are more efficient in their use.

5. Conclusions and suggestions of sustainable landed-housing. Green design parameters both in bioclimatic architecture and green architecture which provide an overview of the use of green design elements in terms of thermal comfort to maximize climate potential both in sun and wind, maximize natural energy and minimize the use of conventional energy, combined with the uniqueness of local wisdom, as follows: The processing techniques are as follows:

5.1. Territory. In developing territory that it is necessary to modify natural topography and vegetation classification techniques, so then it can support the formation of open spaces and recreation technique. Furthermore, the organization circulation technique will be supported by the pedestrian ways technique, which will prioritize proximity to public transportation as a technique. In addition, the techniques of specific form and space-mass proportion is needed in order to know the technique of energy, water and waste supply systems to be integrated into the building.

5.2. Bulding. During the climate condition that facade orientation technique is needed in placing buildings that it is oriented north-south and technique of shading strategies can be used to protect the east-west side. Moreover, the thermal efficiency of building envelope technique is needed as a way to reduce sunlight when perpendicular to the building. In addition, to avoid humidity in a room that is not exposed to sunlight that a temperature comfort technique is needed with modification, then an airflow and infiltration technique so that the airflow can be changed so that humidity can be avoided. Furthermore, renewable energy back-up technique can be useful as a back-up both in support and also as back-up in shutdown from power plants. In addition, main use energy for building will be prepared to alternative energy consumption technique as a combination by gas or coal flows from the power plants with solar energy. Afterwards, rainwater harvesting technique will be accommodated for use of bathroom then domestic waste disposal will be use wastewater treatment technique for use of water for watering plants.

5.3. Materials. In the use of materials, it is strived to use environmentally friendly materials. In addition, it is not having a major impact on the environment and humans but also being able to support according to its function both in for the territory and building itself so that the technique of material structure uses bamboo, rattan and timber as additional and main structures of depending on the building type. Furthermore, the use of materials for inside the building or outside the building still refers to the equipment technique that it consumes less energy, for instance lighting. In addition, the development of territory and buildings cannot be separated from ecological techniques. In particular, wetlands, garden sanitation and recreational park.

Conclusion. So the point is energy efficiency can reduce resource consumption with solar-based energy systems and daytime lighting systems. In a solar-based energy system, the factors that must be considered are the system of use, the orientation of the building, the location of use, the angle of inclination and temperature, as a factor of consideration. On the other hand, daylight lighting system factors that can be used as references include: fenestration, material, area or size, shape, orientation, and ceiling height, so careful design is needed to optimize the quality of the luminous environment for its occupants. Correspondingly, to reduce and reuse in this case recycle the use of

domestic water, bring savings in water, and reduce the environmental impact of water discharge so as to have a positive impact on carbon emissions that help combat climate change, and reduce the threat of water shortages that will come and last but not least, proper waste disposal and management can be done by applying the 3R – Reduce, Reuse and Recycle. Moreover, green design concept can be solving the problems on landed-housing in Bintan island then deficiencies in regional structuring both in infrastructure and settlement, as well as environmental quality including supporting energy efficiency in settlement that leads to good health and well-being in community.

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**РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ПО РАЗРАБОТКЕ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЖИЛЬЯ
НА ОСТРОВЕ БИНТАН, ИНДОНЕЗИЯ**

Аннотация. Индонезия – стремительно развивающаяся страна, четвёртая в мире по численности населения и четырнадцатая по занимаемой территории, при этом она имеет неравномерную плотность населения в различных регионах. Актуальность строительства энергоэффективного жилья в западной Индонезии вызвана, с одной стороны, необходимостью создания новых населённых пунктов для переселения жителей из наиболее переуплотнённых районов и, с другой стороны, их обеспечением экологичными возобновляемыми источниками энергии. В работе анализируется остров Бинтан – самый большой остров в провинции Кепулауан-Рио, расположенный на границе с Сингапуром и Малайзией, характеризующийся экзотической природой и климатом и обладающий большим туристическим, культурным и промышленным потенциалом. Целью исследования является разработка рекомендаций по проектированию малоэтажного жилья на острове Бинтан с учетом эффективного использования ресурсов, защиты биоразнообразия и сохранения экологической целостности природных ресурсов в регионе. Рекомендации имеют трёхуровневую иерархию, включающую аспекты территориального развития, особенности объемно-пространственной структуры зданий и сооружений, а также характеристики применяемых материалов.

Ключевые слова: региональный климат, развитие поселений и зданий, устойчивое землепользование, рекомендации по экологичному дизайну.